

DRIP IRRIGATION SYSTEM IN COTTON.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8347796>

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada paxta tomchilatib sug'orish tizimining afzalliklari va kamchiliklari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Kalit so'zlar: Paxta, tomchilatib sug'orish tizimi, hosildorlik.

Аннотация: В этой статье представлена информация о преимуществах и недостатках системы капельного орошения хлопка. Ключевые слова: Хлопок, система капельного орошения, урожайность.

Abstract: This article provides information on the advantages and disadvantages of cotton drip irrigation system.

Keywords: Cotton, drip irrigation system, yield.

It is known that cotton growing in Uzbekistan is of great importance in the national economy. Therefore, in order to improve the lifestyle of the people of our independent republic, it is necessary to comprehensively develop national agriculture and other sectors of the national economy. In particular, the President of our Republic Sh.M. Mirziyoev and the Cabinet of Ministers have been paying great attention to the development of cotton cultivation and increasing its disease resistance. For this purpose, strengthening cooperation between cotton mills and growers, making science production dependent, is considered an important factor in the development of plans in all areas. Many scientific research institutes of cotton cultivation are being developed using modern methods. In order to ensure the implementation of the decision of our President on December 11, 2020 "On the adoption of measures to accelerate the introduction of water-saving technologies in agriculture", a wide range of water-saving technologies is implemented construction works are being carried out at a rapid pace. 18 Scientific, remote, online conference "Natural sciences in the modern world: Theoretical and practical researches" Correct irrigation regimes are important for obtaining a high yield from cotton. In this regard, it is appropriate to widely introduce the drip irrigation system in cotton cultivation in our country. Although the drip irrigation system appeared in the 19th century, it was used only in small gardens and vegetable gardens. In the drip irrigation system, water enters the cotton field through special pipes connected to the main water source. They have dippers inside that let water flow directly

under the roots of each plant. Depending on the different diameters of pipes, taps, drops, it is possible to change the irrigation rate for crops, that is, it is determined where there is more water and where it is less. The fact is that the more perfect the system, the more expensive it is, the higher the result of drip irrigation. It should not be forgotten that the part where the drip irrigation system of cotton fields is introduced is fully self-sustaining. Advantages of drip irrigation - When crops are drip-irrigated, water is not absorbed into the soil in vain; - Water is not released from the field to waste, as a result, a large part of the water planned for use in irrigation is saved; - In drip irrigation, only the area where crops are planted is irrigated; - In drip irrigation, water is saved up to 2 times; - Productivity is 1.5-1.7 times higher than the average productivity up to 40-45 centners. - In the drip irrigation system, you can add a stream of liquid fertilizer. This will make it easier for you not only to water, but also to feed the plants. - The development of some drought-related diseases is prevented because the soil is always wet under the plant. - Thermal and chemical burns do not occur due to the fact that the leaves are irrigated directly under the roots. Are there any disadvantages of the drip irrigation system? - Dropper tubes can become clogged, resulting in no flow of water. - The root system can develop very densely due to the accumulation of moisture in one place. It should also be noted that it was spent on the introduction of modern drip irrigation systems 25% of the funds will be paid to organizations that grow clusters and other raw cotton 19 "Natural sciences in the modern world: Theoretical and practical research" material, and 50% to farms as a subsidy from the state budget.

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